

The impact of harvesting operation on Albic Retisols in the middle taiga of the Komi Republic

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Forest soils perform important biospheric functions related to the atmosphere, hydrosphere, lithosphere, and the biosphere as a whole. Forest ecosystems are involved in the regulation of carbon and nitrogen cycles in the biosphere, influence the water and temperature regimes of soils, contribute to the formation of river flows and water balance, and control the intensity of pedogenesis and formation of the soil profiles. Soils of forest ecosystems are the major player in the energy processes in the biosphere and sensitively respond to the occurring changes. Cuttings are the most important factor that influences the forest-forming process. The replacement of conifers by leaved tree species has taken place within considerable areas in the northeast of the European part of Russia. A specific feature of the Komi Republic is natural restoration of tree species takes place in cutting areas. The aim of this work is to assess changes in Retisols in the first decades after clear-cutting carried out using modern logging equipment.

The objects of the study were located in the middle taiga of the European part of Russian Federation. To assess the consequences, blueberry spruce and birch forests formed on Retisols in the clear cutting area of eight and eighteen years were selected. It has been found that heavy logging equipment significantly changes forest soils. About 20 percent of the logging areas are represented by skidding trails with mechanically changed soils. Depending on the location in the landscape, in the first decades the soils may be over-watered or, on the contrary, drier compared to the background objects. Logging activities significantly affect the carbon pool in woody vegetation. It was found that coarse woody debris formed during logging decomposes to a significant extent in the first decades after logging. An increase in soil respiration on skidding trails by 1.7–2.5 times was revealed compared to undisturbed areas. Carbon stocks in soils remain fairly stable and are less susceptible to change.

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